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**ASSESSMENT OF ABACA DISEASE MANAGEMENT PROJECT
OF PHILIPPINE FIBER INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT
AUTHORITY IN MANITO, ALBAY**

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25 August 2022

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Acceptance Page:

This Special Problem titled “**Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Project of Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Clark B. Barquilla is an agricultural engineer by profession. He took Bachelor of Science in Agricultural Engineering at Bicol University College of Agriculture and Forestry. He has a strong passion for agriculture and advocates farm mechanization and modernization.

He is currently connected with the Engineering Section of Fiber Utilization and Technology Division of the Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority holding the position of Fiber Development Officer. Being in a research and development institution, the author has the function to design, modify, and develop new machines and devices to hasten the fiber production and provide an additional livelihood for farmers and other stakeholders. The author is also engaged in the transfer of technology to farmer cooperatives and other recipients of the developed technology through training and demonstration. One of his contributions was the establishment of Fiber Processing Centers for Banana, Pineapple, Sisal, Maguey, Cotton, and *Buntal* (Buri). He designed the Fiber Drying Shed and made cost estimates for the mentioned project.

As a researcher, he is currently into research and development of a machine for bamboo fiber extraction. The author is very passionate about utilizing bamboo for various uses such as in furniture, construction materials, and fabrics since it is the best alternative for woods. It takes only three years to fully mature and harvest, unlike the woods which take decades before harvest. Upon graduation from the master's program, he wants to continue supporting the advocacy of planting bamboo in landslide-prone areas and riverbanks. This will also provide a livelihood for locals which gives them an avenue to endure the project.

Before being employed in PhilFIDA, he worked as Technical Assistant in the Regional Agricultural Engineering Division of the Department of Agriculture Regional Field Office V and Engineer I at the Technical Assistance Unit of PhilFIDA Region IV.

The author will continuously uphold the development of agriculture and protection of the environment for our future generations. He believes that national development is achievable in a sustainable manner.

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgement has been made in the text to other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

ENGR. CLARK B. BARQUILLA

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Chapters	Page
Preliminary Pages	
Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Sheet	iii
Bibliographical Sketch	iv
Declaration	v
Acknowledgements	vi
Table of contents	viii
List of tables	xii
List of figures.	xiii
List of appendices	xvi
Abstract	xvii
I. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Background of the Study	1
1.2. Objectives.	3
1.3. Conceptual Framework	3
II. REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES	5
AND LITERATURE	
III. METHODOLOGY	8
3.1. Location of the Study	8
3.2. Respondents	9
3.3. Research Instrument	9
3.4. Data Gathering Procedure	11

3.5. Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis	13
IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	18
4.1. Effectiveness of the ADMP	18
4.1.1. Data Analysis on the Effectiveness	18
of ADMP Project	
4.1.2. Paired Sample T-Test and Pearson	20
Correlation Analysis of Each Barangay	
4.1.2.1. Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay	20
4.1.2.2. Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay	21
4.1.2.3. Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay	22
4.1.2.4. Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay	23
4.2. Disease Incidence During the 5-Year Period	24
Implementation of the Project	
4.3. Socio-Demographic Profiles and ADMP	25
Impacts to the Respondents	
4.3.1. Socio-Demographic Profiles	26
4.3.1.1. Age group	26
4.3.1.2. Sex of the respondents	27
4.3.1.3. Civil status of the respondents	28
4.3.1.4. Highest educational attainment	29
of the respondents	
4.3.1.5. Other sources of income of the	30
respondents	
4.3.1.6. Number of children of the	31
respondents	

4.3.2. Impacts of the Project	32
4.3.2.1. Socio-Economic Impact	32
of the Project		
4.3.2.1.1. Increase in abaca	32
fiber harvested		
4.3.2.1.2. Farmers increased	33
expenditure due to		
increased Income		
4.3.2.1.3. Respondents' perception	34
on the project's success		
4.3.2.1.4. Major contribution of	35
the ADMP project		
4.3.2.2. Gender Equality Impacts	36
4.3.2.2.1. Women's participation	36
in community organization		
4.3.2.2.2. Women's involvement	36
in production activities		
4.3.2.2.3. Women's role in the family	37
4.3.2.2.4. Women's income	37
4.3.2.2.5. Husband and wife role	37
in abaca fiber production		
4.3.2.3. Impacts on Social Capital.	38
4.3.2.3.1. Farmer-Beneficiaries Who	38
Became Members of the		
Organization		

4.3.2.3.2. Community Services Get Accessed by Farmer-Beneficiaries	. . .	39
4.3.2.3.3. Solidarity Among Abaca Farmers	. . .	39
4.3.2.4. Other Impacts	40
4.3.2.4.1. Increase in training and skills development attended	40
4.3.2.4.2. Abaca farming as stable source of income	41
4.3.2.4.3. Abaca farming comparing to other crops as source of livelihood	41
4.3.2.4.4. Change in abaca farming management after the project was implemented	42
4.4. Correlation Amongst Socio-Demographic Profiles, Increase in Abaca Fiber Harvested, and Perception on the Success of the Project	42
V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	45
Bibliography	50
Appendices	51

List of Tables

Table	Page
3.1 Number of Farmer-Beneficiaries Interviewed	9
3.2 Description of Explanatory Variables Used in the Study	14
4.1 Data on Disease Incidence as per Monitored by PhilFIDA-ADMP Team	19
4.2 Correlation Analysis of the Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents, Increased in Abaca Fiber Harvested and FBs Perception on the Success of the Project	44

List of Figures

Figure		Page
1.1	Conceptual Framework of the Study	4
3.1	Location Map of Manito, Albay	8
3.2	Health and safety protocol during respondent's interview	13
4.1	T-test to compare the means of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay	20
4.2	Pearson correlation coefficient of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay	21
4.3	T-test to compare the means of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay	21
4.4	Pearson correlation coefficient of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay	22
4.5	T-test to compare the means of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring	22

	(IDM) in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay	
4.6	Pearson correlation coefficient of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay	23
4.7	T-test to compare the means of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay	24
4.8	Pearson correlation coefficient of % Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and % Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay	24
4.9	Trend of Abaca Disease Incidence during the Five-Year Period Implementation of the Project	25
4.10	Age Group of the Respondents	27
4.11	Sex Group of the Respondents	28
4.12	Civil Status Group of the Respondents	29
4.13	Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents	30
4.14	Other Sources of Income of the Respondents	31
4.15	Number of Children of the Respondents	32
4.16	Increase in Abaca Fiber Harvested	33

4.17	Abaca Farmers Expending from Increased Income	34
4.18	Respondents Respond on the Success of the ADMP Project	35
4.19	Major Contribution of the ADMP Project	36
4.20	Farmer-Beneficiaries Who Became Members of the Organization	38
4.21	Community Services Had Accessed by Farmer-Beneficiaries	39
4.22	Respondents Respond if the Project Caused Solidarity Among Abaca Farmers	42

List of Appendices

Appendices	Page
A Letter to Exec. Dir. Kennedy T. Costales . . .	92
B Letter to OIC-Reg. Dir. Mary Anne R. Molina . . .	93
C Letter to Mayor Joshua Mari C. Daep . . .	94
D Letter to Brgy. Captain Jessie D. Payte . . .	95
E Letter to Brgy. Captain Benito A. Gualvez . . .	96
F Letter to Brgy. Captain Anita B. Ardales . . .	97
G Letter to Brgy. Captain Juan A. Ortiz . . .	98
H Documentations	99
I Questionnaire	100

Abstract

Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Project of Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay.

Abaca farming is one of the major sources of income of farmers living in the four barangays of Manito, Albay consist of Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot. Unfortunately, this livelihood is threatened by the spread of abaca diseases such as abaca bunchy top, bract mosaic, and abaca mosaic which the mosaic has been one of the major factors contributing in decreased crop productivity. This study evaluates the effectiveness of the Abaca Disease Management Project of Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay based from the gathered secondary data and field interviews. The socio-demographic profile of the respondents was gathered to understand its correlation on farmer's perception whether the project is effective or not. The impacts of the project are discussed specifically the socio-economic, gender equality, social capital and other impacts. Out of 125 farmer-beneficiaries, 57 abaca farmers were interviewed. It was found that the ADMP conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay was effective in controlling and eradicating abaca diseases. Majority of farmers interviewed believed that ADMP was successful. The major contribution of the project to the farmer's household increased in fiber harvested, families enabled to send their children to school and abaca farming became their major source of income. Women had equal chance to participate in community organizations. The number of farmer-beneficiaries attending the training and skill development like training on abaca disease control and eradication and livelihood training on abaca fiber processing increased. Respondent's role in abaca farming had high and middle degree of correlation to the increase of abaca fiber harvested, also to

the perceived success of the project. Increase in abaca fiber harvested by the farmers had positive correlation to their perception that ADMP would be a successful project. However, the status of ownership of the land being cultivated, the size of the farm, the age, the sex, the civil status, the education, and the number of children of the farmers had no correlation to the increase of abaca fiber harvested and to the farmer's perception on the success of the project. Results of the study could be valuable for the implementing agency and local government unit in reviewing their project implementation, management and policy-making.

Keywords: disease management, implementation, monitoring, impact

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

Abaca, internationally known as Manila hemp, is endemic to the Philippines. About 85% of the world market consumption for abaca fiber is supplied by the Philippines which generates a total of US\$111.5 million earnings in 2018 (PhilFIDA, 2018). The remaining share of the supply of abaca fibers in the world market is from Ecuador and Costa Rica. The huge economic value of abaca is a driving force in Philippine agriculture with an industry that supports the livelihood of nearly 1.5 million Filipinos including 122,758 farmers who cultivate a total of 180,302 hectares of abaca (PhilFIDA, 2018).

Almost one-third of the abaca areas can be found in Region V or the Bicol Region with 52,493 hectares. Exports of abaca fiber and manufacture generated an average of US\$97.1 million per year in the last ten years. Some US\$84.9 million come from abaca manufactures such as pulp, cordage, yarns, fabrics, and fiber crafts. The remaining US\$12.2 million is from raw fiber exports. Europe, specifically, the United Kingdom, is the premier destination of abaca fiber followed by Asia, with Japan as the leading buyer. All abaca pulps are exported for specialty paper manufactures (Philippine Abaca Roadmap 2018-2022).

The Philippine abaca is more versatile in applications, and it possesses the full spectrum of the quality of abaca that specialty paper manufacturers need. Aside from its various uses and its superior strength, the Abaca fiber helps meet the growing demand for environment-friendly material, being a natural fiber. The abaca plant is

also good for the environment as it helps improve the water holding capacity of the soil, thereby preventing soil erosion, floods, and landslides.

The Philippine abaca industry has maintained its status as the world's largest producer of abaca fiber and continues to maintain a strong position in both international and domestic markets, generating US\$113.33 million annually (PhilFIDA 2016, unpublished). However, the abaca industry is faced with various constraints including damage due to virus diseases (Parac *et al.*, 2021).

Abaca production is also a source of livelihood for Filipino farmers. However, the abaca industry is faced with various constraints, and virus diseases such as abaca bunchy top, bract mosaic, and abaca mosaic have been one of the major factors contributing to decreased crop productivity. The bunchy top disease is the most destructive and widespread viral disease of abaca and banana in the Philippines. The estimated abaca fiber yield losses in 2002 due to abaca bunchy top and mosaic diseases costs at ₱18.3 million in Bicol region and ₱8.4 million in Eastern Visayas region (Sta. Cruz *et al.*, 2016).

The Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority (PhilFIDA) is an attached agency of the Department of Agriculture in which one of the mandates is to promote the growth and development of the natural fiber industry. Through this, PhilFIDA conduct the Abaca Disease Management Project (ADMP) to strategize the abaca disease control and eradication. The project treats infected abaca plants by puncturing herbicide-soaked bamboo sticks, blanket spraying of green-labeled herbicide to all abaca plants. This also utilizes farm-workers in the infected abaca area in collaboration with the LGU and farmers' association.

In 2016, the ADMP started in Manito Albay covering four barangays namely Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan, and Nagotgot comprising an abaca land area of 300

hectares. The municipality of Manito was selected for ADMP due to its high incidence of disease.

1.2. Objectives

The research paper aims to determine the effectiveness of the Abaca Disease Management Project conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay, and to assess its contribution to household beneficiaries and impact on the industry as a whole. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the effectiveness of the ADMP based from the gathered secondary data
2. Describe the trend of disease incidence over the 5-year implementation of the project
3. Ascertain the impacts of the project at the individual household as well as industry levels; and
4. Identify the relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profiles and impact of the project.

1.3. Conceptual Framework

The prevalence of abaca diseases causes the decrease in the production of fiber and poses a threat to the industry as a whole. The Philippine supplies about 85% of the world market consumption for abaca fiber.

To protect the industry, the Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority implemented the Abaca Disease Management Project (ADMP) to control the spread of the disease and to eradicate it.

Consequently, this study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of the ADMP in controlling and eradicating the diseases and also to assess its contribution to farmer-beneficiaries (FBs) of the project as well as to the Philippine abaca industry as a whole. Contribution were assessed through its impacts on socio-economic, gender equality, socio-capital and other impacts.

The effectiveness of the project was measured by two sets of variables namely Disease Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and Disease Incidence During Monitoring (IDM). The relationship of socio-demographic profile of the respondents to their perception on the success of the project was analyzed. The increase in fiber production and income of the respondents also determined if correlated to respondent’s perception on the success of the project.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES AND LITERATURE

Importance of Abaca

Abaca (*Musa textilis*) is a plant related to the banana. It is indigenous to the Philippines, and grows well particularly in the provinces of Bicol, Samar and Leyte. Abaca is also one of the few cash crops that can grow with relatively little input compared to other crops, in steep forest areas. For this reason, it is often the crop of choice of households living in villages at the forest edge. The study shows that abaca is an important secondary income source of households with lowland farms, and frequently the only source of cash income of the poorest households in the community (Richman, 2002).

Epidemiology and Integrated Management of Abaca Bunchy Top in the Bicol Region

In Bicol region, man apparently plays a significant role as an agent of dispersal of the vector and indirectly of the virus. In the course of normal farm activities, notably cultural operations and harvesting, man disturbs the natural habitat of the vector triggering more than normal movement of non-alate forms and flight of the alate forms. These movements appear to be localized as indicated by current aggregated disease distribution in specific towns (Raymundo and Bajet, 2000).

One of the major undertakings of PhilFIDA is the implementation of the Abaca Disease Management Program (ADMP) that aims to eradicate and rehabilitate disease-infected abaca areas (Galvez *et al.*, 2021).

Eradication and Vector Control by Chemical Spray

The destruction of infected plants is the primary objective of the eradication program. Along with this, is an attempt to prevent the dispersal of the virus by reducing, if not eliminating, the insect vector. Several approaches have been tried:

Cutting of an infected plant at the base by using a bolo does not eliminate the virus source as infected regrowth will appear in due time as aforementioned. To dig the corms out, as sometimes practiced, is too laborious and costly not to consider the built-in resistance of the farmers in eradicating the virus. Piercing infected plants with a bamboo stick previously dipped in an herbicide solution is a fast way of covering a wide area and has been done with much success. However, regrowth still appears due to inconsistency of the operation. Currently, the procedure being followed involves cutting down of diseased plants at the base, boring a hole at the center of the corm, and dropping 5 cc of herbicide. Regrowth appears at the periphery of mats which are in an advanced state of decomposition but eliminating these has become a lot easier. This practice has been quite successful.

The abovementioned eradication procedure is complemented by chemical spray that is applied beforehand and is intended to kill the vector before it is disturbed and has the opportunity to escape. This spray is directed towards the bunchy top affected area and its immediate surrounding.

The current approach involves first the targeting of identified “hot spots”, local concentrations of disease, in order to drastically reduce the source of inoculum in a region. Thereafter, eradication will be directed at adjoining areas. At the same time, areas which are not affected yet will be protected. This protection takes the form of early monitoring and prompt removal of infected plants. Although bunchy top can be found all over the Bicol Region, there are areas that somehow have remained

apparently disease-free. Whether abaca plants in these areas are bunchy top virus-free or not has not been determined (Raymundo and Bajet, 2000).

Overview of the ADMP Project

The occurrences of viral diseases in abaca farms have been persistent since the 1980s. In the later part of 1980s, the Government through the Department of Agriculture (DA) has provided fund for the Fiber Industry Development Authority (FIDA) to implement the “Integrated Pest Management Project Phase I” (IPM I) particularly in selected abaca areas in the Bicol Region. The Abaca Disease Control and Eradication as a major component of the Project was aimed to reduce the percentage disease incidence particularly in Albay province.

This Project was followed in the early 1990s with the implementation of the “Integrated Pest Management Project Phase II” (IPM II). Again, as one of the components of the Project, it sustained the abaca disease eradication covering not only Albay but the nearby provinces of Sorsogon, Camarines Sur and Catanduanes.

It was in 2009 and 2010 that FIDA was given P15M and P10.461M respectively, by the Department of Budget and Management which was incorporated in the 2009 and 2010 General Appropriation of FIDA to implement the “Abaca Disease Management Project.” This was complemented by the Department of Agriculture through the High Value Commercial Crops (HVCC) Project, which provided a budget of P10.2M to FIDA in 2009 to augment its fund to arrest the spread of the abaca diseases in selected abaca producing areas.

According to ADMP Implementation Manual, the project had the objective to control the spread of abaca diseases at the manageable level of 0% to less than 5% level of the target areas.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Location of the Study

The study was conducted in four (4) barangays in the Municipality of Manito, Albay consisting of Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot. These barangays were identified by PhilFIDA with a high incidence of abaca disease.

Figure 3.1. Location Map of Manito, Albay

3.2. Respondents

A total of fifty-seven (57) respondents from 125 listed farmer-beneficiaries of the project were interviewed in the study. Purposive sampling was employed to select the respondents with the assistance of the PhilFIDA Regional Office V, Municipal Agriculture Office of Manito, and Barangay Local Government Units (BLGUs).

The qualified respondents were selected from the master list of farmer-beneficiaries provided by PhilFIDA Regional Office V based from the accessibility of the location of the farmers.

Table 3.1

Number of Farmer-Beneficiaries Interviewed

Barangay	Farmer-beneficiaries (FBs)	No. of Respondents Interviewed	Percentage (%)
Balasbas	24	16	66.67
Buyo	41	13	31.71
Cawayan	27	14	51.85
Nagotgot	21	14	66.67
Total	125	57	45.60

3.3. Research Instrument

Data on number of farmers engaged in abaca farming, size of the farm and location of the identified barangay infested by abaca diseases were gathered. The data were all reported in the PhilFIDA 2016 ADMP report. These data are important and relevant to the study as the researcher was enabled to identify the area, name

and target number of respondents to be interviewed, and these served as inputs to the analysis of data.

Secondary data on disease incidence were also gathered. This was done by conducting a review of monitoring reports from 2016 to 2017. Said monitoring was regularly conducted by the ADMP monitoring team organized by PhilFIDA and provided data on disease Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and Incidence During Monitoring (IDM).

After all secondary data were gathered, they were organized and analyzed according to the objectives of this research.

Primary data were gathered through a face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire with response options, to facilitate the accomplishment of the questionnaire by the respondents. Responses provided –by respondents which were not included in the response options were recorded and labeled as “*others*”. Other questions were required a “Yes” or “No” answer from respondents.

The following are the parts of the questionnaire answered by the respondents:

a.) Respondent Identification

This includes personal information of the farmer, legal ownership of the land being cultivated and role in abaca farming activities.

b.) Socio-demographic Profile

The question under this part assesses the relationship of socio-demographics of respondents to their perception on the success of the project.

c.) Socio-economic Impact of the Project

The questions under this portion determine the economic impact of the project to the household beneficiaries. This portion of the questionnaire is not to validate what has been reported in the monitoring but to supplement what was

not covered in ADMP monitoring which focuses only to the changes in disease incidence after the implementation of the project. With this, we can integrate the economic contribution of the project in the farming income or fiber produce by every household beneficiary.

d.) Gender Equality Impact

This part of the questionnaire determines the opportunity opened by the project especially on women which sometimes has marginalized participation in community organizations.

e.) Impact on Social Capital

This portion identifies the membership of the respondents in the association, the access to social services, and the solidarity among members of the community.

f.) Other Impacts

The question under this portion includes the training attended and skills acquired by respondents, stability of abaca farming as stable source of income, and changes in management in abaca farming.

3.4. Data Gathering Procedure

The secondary data were gathered from the monitoring and evaluation report submitted by PhilFIDA-ADMP monitoring team to PhilFIDA Regional Office V. The background of the project and list of the farmer-beneficiaries were provided both by PhilFIDA Central Office and Regional Office V. The General Base Map of the Municipality of Manito, Albay was given by Local Government Unit of Manito through Municipal Planning and Development Coordination Department (MPDCD). The

researcher prepared a letter addressed to PhilFIDA and LGU-Manito requesting that the researcher be given access to the report and relevant information to the project.

Prior to the interview process, letters of communications requesting permission and assistance were sent to the office of the PhilFIDA Region V, MLGU-Manito, and BLGUs. The researcher was accompanied by a technical staff of PhilFIDA Region V assigned in the area, MAO personnel, and officers from BLGUs during the conduct of interview. The assigned technical staff of PhilFIDA Region V and personnel from MAO are known in the area and also familiar with the abaca farmers living in the four barangays which are the subject of the study. This scenario became advantageous for the researcher to select the right respondents and disseminate the information to the farmer-beneficiaries about the survey. Before the scheduled interview, the researcher coordinated with the Office of the OIC-Regional Director of PhilFIDA Region V to set the travel and activities to be conducted in the area. The communication letters to the barangay captains were sent through email to the MAO office. The agricultural technician assigned in abaca commodity was the one who informed the barangay captains and ADMP farmer-beneficiaries team leaders in the areas.

Before going to the area, local health and safety protocol on Covid-19 were observed. Initial coordination with the LGU of Manito was done to check and comply with the requirements. Also, during the face-to-face interview social distancing and wearing of face mask were observed.

Figure 3.2. Health and safety protocol was observed during courtesy visits to the office of PhilFIDA Region V, BLGUs and during respondent's interview.

Before the actual interview, the respondents were briefed on the purpose of the study and they were assured that data to be obtained would be confidential and would be used only for academic purposes.

3.5. Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

The data collected were consolidated using Microsoft Excel. The statistical tools such as frequency distribution, totals and percentages were used in data analysis. Aside from using Microsoft Excel, SPSS software was utilized to compute and analyze the correlation among demographic profile, increased in fiber harvested and FBs perception on the success of the project.

The maps were presented to determine the location of the project study. Graphs were provided to describe the data on socio-demographics of the respondents, contribution, and impacts of the project to the household's beneficiaries. The impact was correlated to the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationships between socio-demographic and respondents' perception on the success of the project. According to Investopedia, the Pearson coefficient is a mathematical correlation coefficient representing the relationship between two variables, denoted as X and Y. Pearson coefficients range

from +1 to -1, with +1 representing a positive correlation, -1 representing a negative correlation, and 0 representing no relationship.

The data on land status, size, membership in cooperative and other socio-demographic variables were converted in numerical value and categorized as nominal, ordinal, interval, or range in order to correlate the socio-demographic profile to perceptions of respondents to the impacts of the project.

Table 3.2

Description of Explanatory Variables Used in the Study

Variable	Description	Unit of Measure
Status of land being cultivated (Nominal)	Categories how the land being acquired by the Respondent	(1) Owned (2) Tenant (3) Agrarian Reform Beneficiary (4) Rented (5) Inherited (6) Others
Size of the farm (Ordinal)	Size of the farm being cultivated by farmer (in ha)	(1) Less than one (2) One (3) Two (4) Three and above
Membership in cooperative (Nominal)	Membership of the respondent in a cooperative or association	(1) Yes (2) No
Role of respondent (Nominal)	Respondent role in abaca farming activities	(1) <i>Tuxero</i> (2) Stripper (3) <i>Tuxero</i> /Stripper (4) Trader (5) Processor (6) Others
Age (Interval)	Age of the Respondent	(1) 20 - 30 (2) 31 - 40 (3) 41 - 50 (4) 51 - 60 (5) 61 and above

Sex (Nominal)	Sex of the Respondent	(1) Male (2) Female
Civil status (Nominal)	Civil status of the respondent	(1) Single (2) Married (3) Legally Separated (4) Annulled (5) Widowed
Educational attainment (Ordinal)	Highest Educational attainment of the Respondent	(1) Did not finish Elementary (2) Elementary Graduate (3) Did not finish High School (4) High School Graduate (5) Vocational Course (6) College Undergraduate (7) College Graduate
Other source of income (Nominal)	Source of Income of the Respondent aside from abaca farming	(1) Government employment (2) Private employment (3) Business owner (4) Rice farming (5) Coconut farming (6) Tiger grass " <i>talahib</i> " farming (7) Vegetable farming (8) Fishing (9) Labor (10) Others
No. of children (Ordinal)	No. of children of respondent	(1) One (2) Two (3) Three (4) Four and above
Increase in harvest (Nominal)	Increased in yield of abaca fiber harvested by respondent after the project was implemented	(1) Yes (2) No
Increase in income (Nominal)	Increased in the income of the respondent after the project was implemented	(1) Yes (2) No
Success of the project (Nominal)	Respondent perception on the success of the ADMP project	(1) Yes (2) No

Contribution of the project (Nominal)	Major contribution of the project to respondent's household	(1) Major source of livelihood (2) Increase in income (3) Enable children to send to school (4) Others, specify: _____ (5) None
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Eradication was the complete reduction of disease incidence to zero through deliberate efforts. However, the ADMP project of PhilFIDA aimed to achieve less than 5% reduction of disease incidence which was manageable at farmer’s level. ADMP project was considered effective if the disease incidence was reduced to less than 5%. Using descriptive statistics, the mean of disease incidence during monitoring must be less than 5 % to categorize its level of effectiveness. The disease incidence was monitored after treatment by PhilFIDA-ADMP monitoring team by sampling. Evaluation was done in the number of hectares monitored, not number of farms when survey locations were sampled. Indicated in the report were the hectarage monitored together with the number of hectarage samples surveyed.

The secondary data gathered for ADMP composed of measures of central tendency and measures of variability. The measure of central tendency is a representation quantitative of the set of data under investigation. The measures of central tendency values tend to lie within the center of the data. The measure of variability indicates how close or widespread the data are from the average. The smaller dispersion of scored arising from the comparison often indicates more consistency and reliability.

Measure of Central Tendency and Variability. Paired sample *t*-test was used to determine whether the mean difference between two sets of observation is zero. In a paired sample *t*-test, each subject was measured twice, resulting in pairs of observation. On the other hand, correlation was a bivariate analysis that measures the

strength of association between two variables and the direction of the relationship. In terms of the strength of relationship, the value of the correlation coefficient varies between +1 and -1. Pearson r correlation was the most widely used correlation statistic to measure the degree of the relationship between linearly related variables.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the findings of the study are presented. The discussion is composed of four parts based from the objectives of the study. These are the effectiveness of the ADMP, the disease incidence over the 5-year implementation of the project, the socio-demographics and impacts of the project, and the relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profiles and impact of the project.

4.1. Effectiveness of the ADMP Project

The analysis of effectiveness of the ADMP project was based from the secondary data provided by PhilFIDA as the implementing agency of the project. The actual area covered refers to the size of the farm while the effective area refers to those areas planted only with abaca. It happens that covered area was not equal to effective area because abaca in the Philippines is planted in the partly shaded areas like under coconut trees or intercropped with other crops. Another reason was abaca is endemic in the Philippines which grow in patches pattern in land. The subject areas for disease control and eradication was 100% covered on the first year of implementation as reflected in the effective areas treated.

4.1.1. Data Analysis on the Effectiveness of ADMP Project

Table 3 shows the computed results of central tendency and variability. Among the four barangays, abaca farm actual area covered has a mean of 41.63 hectares. On the other hand, the mean effective area treated is 26.25 hectares. The mean of

%IDE was 25.32% which was reduced to as low as 2.88% after disease control and eradication was done.

On the first year of implementation, the project was able to attain its objective of reducing the disease incidence into less than 5% which was considered manageable at farmer's level. In terms of variability, the standard deviation of the actual area planted, effective area treated, %IDE, %IDM were 13.30, 11.53, 4.42 and 0.85, respectively.

The effective area was part of the actual area covered which has existing abaca. The effective area treated was determined through geo-tagging which are one of the tools in monitoring and evaluation of government projects.

Based on PhilFIDA set objective, it appeared that the Abaca Disease Management Project was effective in disease management.

Table 4.1

Data on Disease Incidence as per Monitored by PhilFIDA-ADMP Team

Location	Actual Area Covered (ha)	Effective Area Treated (ha)	% Incidence During Eradication (%IDE)	% Incidence During Monitoring (%IDM)
Balabas	46.00	33.00	30.52	3.21
Buyo	22.00	9.00	25.00	2.18
Cawayan	47.00	31.00	19.76	2.20
Nagotgot	51.50	32.00	26.00	3.92
Mean	41.63	26.25	25.32	2.88
Median	46.50	20.50	25.50	2.71
Mode	None	None	None	None
Variance	176.90	132.92	19.51	0.72
Std. Deviation	13.30	11.53	4.42	0.85

4.1.2. Paired Sample T-test and Pearson Correlation Analysis of Each Barangay

4.1.2.1. Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay. The results of paired sample *t*-tests as shown in Fig. 4.1 indicate that there was a significant difference ($t=10.733$, $p=.000$) on the disease incidence after the eradication (application of pesticides, puncturing of insecticide-soaked bamboo, rouging, burning, etc.) in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay.

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	%IDE	30.3750	8	7.42462	2.62500
	%IDM	3.2137	8	1.58471	.56028

Pair	%IDE - %IDM	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
1		27.16125	7.15778	2.53066	21.17720	33.14530	10.733	7	.000

Fig.4.1. T-Test to compare the means of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay

Figure 4.2 shows that there was a negligible correlation between %Incidence During Eradication and %Incidence During Monitoring in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay, which was statistically not significant ($r=.272$, $n=8$, $p=0.05$). This means that increase or decrease in %IDE did not affect the increase or decrease in %IDM.

Correlations

		%IDE	%IDM
%IDE	Pearson Correlation	1	.272
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.514
	N	8	8
%IDM	Pearson Correlation	.272	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.514	
	N	8	8

Fig.4.2. Pearson correlation coefficient of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay

4.1.2.2. Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay. The results of paired sample *t*-tests as presented in Fig. 4.3 show that there was a significant difference ($t=23.057$, $p=.000$) on the disease incidence after the eradication (application of pesticides, puncturing of insecticide-soaked bamboo, rouging, burning, etc.) in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay.

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	%IDE	11.8563	8	1.46907	.51940
	%IDM	2.1775	8	1.35035	.47742

Paired Samples Test

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	%IDE - %IDM	9.6787	1.18732	.41978	8.68613	10.67137	23.057	7	.000
		5							

Fig.4.3. T-Test to compare the means of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay

In Fig.4.4, there was a negligible correlation between % Incidence During Eradication and % Incidence During Monitoring in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay, which was statistically not significant ($r=.648$, $n=8$, $p=0.05$). It means that the increase or the decrease in %IDE and %IDM did not affect each other.

		%IDE	%IDM
%IDE	Pearson Correlation	1	.648
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.082
	N	8	8
%IDM	Pearson Correlation	.648	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.082	
	N	8	8

Fig.4.4. Pearson correlation coefficient of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay

4.1.2.3. Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay. The results of paired sample t-tests are presented in Fig. 4.5. Data show that there was a significant difference ($t=16.087$, $p=.000$) on the disease incidence after the eradication (application of pesticides, puncturing of insecticide-soaked bamboo, rouging, burning, etc.) in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay.

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	%IDE	17.1667	9	2.70261	.90087
	%IDM	2.2013	9	1.32888	.44296

		Paired Differences		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper				

Pair	%IDE -	14.965	2.79082	.93027	12.82012	17.11054	16.087	8	.000
1	%IDM	33							

Fig.4.5. T-Test to compare the means of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay

There was a negligible correlation between %Incidence During Eradication and %Incidence During Monitoring in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay, which was statistically significant ($r=.178$, $n=9$, $p=0.05$) as indicated in Figure 4.6. The negative correlation means that changed in %IDE did not affect to the increase or decrease value of %IDM.

		%IDE	%IDM
%IDE	Pearson Correlation	1	.178
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.646
	N	9	9
%IDM	Pearson Correlation	.178	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.646	
	N	9	9

Fig.4.6. Pearson correlation coefficient of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay

4.1.2.4. Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay. The results of paired sample t-tests shows that there was a significant difference ($t=5.086$, $p=.002$) on the disease incidence after the eradication (application of pesticides, puncturing of insecticide-soaked bamboo, rouging, burning, etc.) in Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay as indicated in Fig. 4.7.

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	%IDE	26.8571	7	12.15769	4.59518
	%IDM	3.9229	7	.78883	.29815

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
Pair					Lower	Upper			
1	%IDE - %IDM	22.934	11.93095	4.50947	11.90000	33.96857	5.086	6	.002

Fig. 4.7. T-Test to compare the means of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay

In Fig. 4.8, there was no relationship between %Incidence During Eradication and %Incidence During Monitoring in Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay, which was statistically not significant ($r=.178$, $n=9$, $p=0.05$). This implied that increased or decreased in %IDE and %IDM were independent from each other.

Correlations			
		%IDE	%IDM
%IDE	Pearson Correlation	1	.317
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.488
	N	7	7
%IDM	Pearson Correlation	.317	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.488	
	N	7	7

Fig. 4.8. Pearson correlation coefficient of %Incidence During Eradication (IDE) and %Incidence During Monitoring (IDM) in Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay

4.2. Disease Incidence during the 5-Year Period Implementation of the Project

The AMDP's objective was to reduce the disease incidence into less than 5% which is manageable at the farmer's level. In 2016, the recorded disease incidence was 25.32% and it was reduced to 2.88% based from the 2017 abaca disease incidence monitoring. Figure 4.9 indicates that during the first year of implementation

of the project, the disease was controlled and eradicated at a level that was manageable for the farmers. Since the disease incidence was reduced to 2.88%, lower than the set objective of less than 5%, PhilFIDA conducted only one-time monitoring of disease incidence in Manito, Albay.

Fig. 4.9. Trend of Abaca Disease Incidence During the Five-Year Period Implementation of the Project

4.3. Socio-demographic Profiles and ADMP Impacts to the Respondents

This section presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and impacts of the project to the farmer-beneficiaries. The profile includes the age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and source/s of income aside from abaca farming.

4.3.1. Socio-Demographic Profiles

4.3.1.1. Age group. Figure 4.10 shows that majority of abaca farmer-beneficiaries were in their old age or senior years at 59.65%. Old aged farmers mostly were residents of Cawayan, Nagotgot and Balasbas at 85.71%, 57.14%, and 50%, respectively. The remaining 50% of abaca farmers in Balasbas were in the middle age. In Buyo, both old aged and middle aged abaca farmers comprised 46% while the remaining 8% were in the youth category. It means that 54% of abaca farmers in Buyo were still in productive age. It was noticeable that the aging farmers in Cawayan at 85.71% were in their senior years while the remaining 14.29% were all in the middle age. The Barangay Nagotgot had still 7.14% of the youth who were engaged in farming and 35.71% were in the middle age bracket. Old aged farmers started at the age of fifty-one while middle age stretched from age 31- 50. According to Republic Act No. 8044 (RA 8044) also known as Youth in Nation-Building Act, youth are a category with persons whose age is between 15 and 30 years old.

Based on the PhilFIDA's 2009 National Survey of Areas Planted to Abaca, most of the abaca farmers in the Philippines fall within the range of 41 to 50 years old, constituting 25% of the abaca farmer population in the country. Following closely were those within the range of 31 to 40 years old and 51 to 60 years old comprising 23 and 18 percent, respectively. Meanwhile, the younger segment of the country's population, i.e. those aged less than 30 years old comprised cumulatively 19% of the respondents.

Comparing the age of abaca farmers in Manito, Albay to the National Survey conducted by PhilFIDA, age within the range of C (51 to 60) and D (61 and above) were both the most age of abaca farmers at 29.82%, followed by age group C (41-50), B (31-40), and A (20-30) representing 22.81, 14.04, and 3.51% of abaca farmers, respectively.

Figure 4.10. Age Group of the Respondents

4.3.1.2. Sex of the respondents. Figure 4.11 shows the dominance of female abaca farmers in Barangay Balasbas with 68.75% female as compared to other three barangays. Conversely, abaca farmers in Barangay Buyo were comprised of 76.92% males. In Barangay Cawayan, there was an equal number of male and female abaca farmers. Lastly, it was noticeable that in Barangay Nagotgot all abaca farmer respondents were male. On the average, there was predominance of male abaca farmers at 63.16% among the respondents.

According to 2009 National Survey of Areas Planted to Abaca, sex distribution shows that 84% of farmers were males while 15% were females.

Figure 4.11. Sex Group of the Respondents

4.3.1.3. Civil status of the respondents. A large number of abaca farmers were married as indicated in Figure 4.12. The married respondents in the following barangays of Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot were 87.50%, 76.92%, 92.86% and 100%, respectively. These consist of 89.47% of the total number of respondents. In Balasbas and Buyo, the percentage of single status engaging in abaca farming was 6.25% and 15.38%, respectively. There was no respondent with single status recorded in Cawayan and Nagotgot. There was one widow in each barangay of Balasbas and Buyo and one legally separated in barangay Cawayan.

Figure 4.12. Civil Status Group of the Respondents

4.3.1.4. Highest educational attainment of the respondents. Figure 4.13 shows that majority of abaca farmers were Elementary graduate which comprises 50.88% of the total respondents, followed by 17.54% who did not finish elementary. Only three respondents (5.26%) were able to graduate in college, one from Buyo and two from Cawayan. The respondents who did not finish College were 3.51%; those who did not finish High School were 15.79%; and 5.26% were High School graduate. Among the 57 respondents, only one had attended a vocational course.

Figure 4.13. Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents

4.3.1.5. Other sources of income of the respondents. It is evident in Fig. 4.14 that aside from abaca farming, farmer-beneficiaries of ADMP project were also engaged in other agricultural activities as their additional source of income; majority of them have multiple sources of livelihood to augment their monthly income. To illustrate, tiger grass farming was engaged by abaca farmers from Balasbas as their other source of income and followed by coconut and rice farming. In Barangay Nagotgot, rice farming has been the other source of income for many abaca farmers; others were paid as wage workers, some were privately employed and the rest were in the government service. Abaca farmers in Barangay Cawayan were mostly engaged in labor, rice farming, vegetable farming, business and other sources of income. In order of frequency, tiger grass, rice and coconut farming were the other major sources of income of farmers in Barangay Buyo while few were engaged in paid labor and other jobs. It was observed that all abaca farmers in four barangays were engaged in

rice farming. Other sources of income of the respondents include pili (*Canarium ovatum*) farming, banana (*Musa*) farming, and running an owned sari-sari store. Some were earning extra income as jeepney driver and jeepney dispatcher.

Figure 4.14. Other Sources of Income of the Respondents

4.3.1.6. Number of children of the respondents. The majority (67.86%) of abaca farmers in all barangay had four and above number of children as shown in Fig 4.15. Looking at the percentage of households in barangays Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot, it is evident that there were 50%, 66.67%, 92.86% and 64.29% of households with children between four and above, respectively.

Figure 4.15. Number of Children of the Respondents

4.3.2. IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

4.3.2.1. Socio-economic Impact of the Project

4.3.2.1.1. Increase in abaca fiber harvested. Figure 4.16 shows that respondents from the barangays of Cawayan and Nagotgot noticed a 100% increase in abaca fiber harvested after the ADMP was implemented in 2016. However, respondents reported an increase in fiber harvested at 87.50% and 15.38%, in barangays Balasbas and Buyo, respectively. Abaca farmers who did not experience increase in abaca fiber harvested, associated it with the occurrence of typhoons during the wet season that hit their abaca farms while some farmers associated it to the prevalence of abaca diseases.

Figure 4.16. Increase in Abaca Fiber Harvested

4.3.2.1.2. Farmers increased expenditure due to increased income. One of the impacts of project to beneficiaries was increased income during project implementation. The Barangay Buyo recorded the highest increase in farmer's income at 10% followed by Cawayan, Balasbas and Nagotgot at 9%, 6% and 5% income increase, respectively.

The study probed into the expenditures of farmer-beneficiaries given their increased income. Figure 4.17 shows that famers mainly used their additional income to purchase food, clothing, medicine, pay cost of education of their children, electric and water bill. In other words, all of their expenses from increased income were devoted to attending to their basic necessities. Buying furniture and house construction/repair were not their priorities since they have other sources of livelihood and income alone from abaca farming for most farmers was not sufficient for such expenses, which to them were luxurious. Among the respondents, only one abaca

farmer said that increased in their family income from abaca farming was used to expand the farm area by planting more abaca seedlings.

Figure 4.17. Abaca Farmers Expending from Increased Income

4.3.2.1.3. Respondents' perception on the project's success. Majority of respondents at 89.47% believed that ADMP of the PhilFiDA is a successful project as shown in Fig 4.18. The percentages of respondents who believed that ADMP was a successful project in the barangays of Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot were at 87.50%, 69.23%, 100% and 100%, respectively. Some abaca farmers who responded that ADMP was not successful said that they did not experience increase in income and continuously observed the presence of diseases on their farm.

Figure 4.18. Respondents Respond on the Success of the ADMP Project

4.3.2.1.4. Major contribution of the ADMP project. Figure 4.19 indicates that increased in income was the major contribution of the ADMP to the farmer-beneficiaries as reported by half (50.54%) of the respondents. In addition, ADMP project also had an impact on the farmers by way of contributing to their family income that enabled them to send their children to school as reported by 27.96% of respondents. Abaca farming became the major source of income for some abaca farmers which consist of 16.13%. About 5.38% of respondents said that ADMP has no contribution to their household since they did not experience increase in income due to the diseases that continue to prevail in their abaca farms. In addition, some abaca areas were hit by typhoons that resulted to other farmers shifting to other production activities such as tiger grass, rice and coconut farming.

Figure 4.19. Major Contribution of the ADMP Project

4.3.2.2. Gender Equality Impacts

4.3.2.2.1. Women's participation in community organization. Based on interviews and reports, women had equal chance as the male beneficiaries in community organization (CO) participation. For instance, in Barangay Balasbas, women abaca farmer-beneficiaries of the project were also members of Balasbas Abaca Development Cooperative (BADECO). Women in four barangays were actively participating in the training on livelihood conducted by PhilFIDA but had no formal association or cooperative had been formed or organized.

4.3.2.2.2. Women's involvement in production activities. The fiber produced in Manito, Albay was of high quality, which was suitable raw material in handicraft making. Produced by their husband, the abaca fiber used by women was mainly for handicraft making such as abaca twine, ropes, scrunch, slippers, macrame

bags, *sinamay* and other products. However, the farmers needed to sometimes source out the supply of abaca fiber from other places due to high demand for raw materials for handicraft production. Others were being supplied of raw materials by handicraft traders.

4.3.2.2.3. Women's role in the family. Women generally played the role of a housewife and did not engage in outdoor chores like abaca fiber production. However, since abaca fiber was produced in the area that served as raw material for producing handicrafts, women had the opportunity to engage in handicraft making.

4.3.2.2.4. Women's income. Handicraft making had been the primary source of income for women living in four barangays due to abundance of raw materials for handicraft. Aside from abaca fiber used for handicraft, *walis tambo* (whisk broom) making was also an additional source of income since the barangays are abundant in tiger grass (*Thysanolaena latifolia*).

4.3.2.2.5. Husband and wife role in abaca fiber production. In the study site, husbands usually did the extraction of abaca fiber through tuxying and stripping. Abaca fiber production was a very laborious process from topping, tumbling, tuxying, stripping, drying and baling which usually done by men. A wife focused on handicraft making using raw materials provided by her husband. Therefore, there were specific different roles performed by men and women in the study sites in abaca fiber production and its by-products.

4.3.2.3. Impacts on Social Capital

4.3.2.3.1. Farmer-Beneficiaries Who Became Members of the Organization

Figure 4.20 shows that small percentage (19.30%) of abaca farmers became members of the organization. The farmer-beneficiaries who became members of the organizations in Balasbas and Buyo were 31.25% and 46.15%, respectively. There were no abaca farmers who became members of the organization in Barangays Cawayan and Nagotgot. The barangay of Balasbas formed an organization called the Balasbas Abaca Development Cooperative (BADECO) while in Buyo the abaca farmers were also members of other organizations. The farmer's organizations present in Buyo were Manito Abaca Development Cooperative, Manito Palaycheck Federation, and Bicol Center for Community Development. The project had no direct influence to the farmer-beneficiaries in joining other organizations since they belonged to other programs by Municipal Agriculture Office and NGO. It was observed that the project had little influence for farmers to form a group which can serve as an avenue for farmers to gain new knowledge and develop social skills including leadership.

Figure 4.20. Farmer-Beneficiaries Who Became Members of the Organization

4.3.2.3.2. Community Services Get Accessed by Farmer-Beneficiaries

As can be gleaned in Fig. 4.21, only a small number of farmer-beneficiaries had access in the community services offered such as transportation and credit assistance for farmers. Only a few (17.54%) of the farmers were given access to transportation through Farm-to-Market Road (FMR) project of the Department of Agriculture and credit assistance from the Local Government Unit of Manito, Albay through the MAO. On the other hand, farmers in Balasbas and Buyo had access to community services; specifically, 6.29% of farmers in Balasbas had an access to transportation while farmers in Buyo had access to both transportation and credit assistance as revealed by 53.85 and 15.38% of the respondents, respectively.

Figure 4.21. Community Services Had Accessed by Farmer-Beneficiaries (FBs)

4.3.2.3.3. Solidarity Among Abaca Farmers

Farmers from Barangays Cawayan and Nagotgot believed that the ADMP caused solidarity among them as shown in Figure 4.22. Conversely, respondents from

Balabas and Buyo did not agree that there was solidarity developed among them, saying that abaca farmers were still independent from each other. For example, some respondents in Balabas and Buyo cited that they were still on their own in managing their abaca farm. Furthermore, the individual initiative of each farmer on how to develop and improve their method of abaca farming remained.

Figure 4.22. Respondents Respond if the Project Caused Solidarity Among Abaca Farmers

4.3.2.4. Other Impacts

4.3.2.4.1. Increase in training and skills development attended. The farmer-beneficiaries of the project were trained by PhilFIDA on how to control and eradicate the abaca diseases by puncturing herbicide-soaked bamboo sticks and blanket spraying of green labeled herbicide to all abaca plants while other infected plants were rouged and burned. PhilFIDA emphasized the importance of attending the trainings they initiated on the part of the farmers since abaca farm owners were not trained, and

that forced them to pay instead trained individuals to do the puncturing of bamboo sticks with chemicals and spraying of herbicides for them.

Women were trained for handicraft making since the quality of fiber produced in the area was of the higher grade, which was purposely used for handicraft making.

4.3.2.4.2. Abaca farming as stable source of income. The respondents believed that the abaca farming could be a stable source of income if the abaca is free from diseases. Since most of the respondents belonged to the next generation of abaca farmers, it is very important for the parents to pass on the knowledge and skills in abaca farming to their children.

4.3.2.4.3. Abaca farming comparing to other crops as source of livelihood. Abaca had been a good source of sustainable income for many because of its ability to recover quickly from a strike of typhoon compared to other crops like coconut and tiger grass. Even after the typhoon, the damaged matured stalks could still be harvested for fiber extraction. According to the farmers, the abaca suckers became more flourished especially after the typhoon, making them produce more stalks for harvest. Furthermore, for them, it would be better to engage in abaca farming for it requires only a one-time planting but continuous harvest. Abaca could be harvested every three months from the first harvest. It would take 24 months for abaca to become mature and ready for harvest. Unlike in tiger grass farming in which majority of the respondents were engaged, farmers could harvest one time only in a year and replanting would be needed again. According to them, abaca farming was much better than coconut farming due to cheaper price of copra and coconut aside from the fact

that it would take a long time for coconut to recover after devastation caused by typhoon.

4.3.2.4.4. Change in abaca farming management after the project was implemented. The farmer-beneficiaries of the project expressed that there was a change in management of abaca farming, especially in disease management. Abaca farmers learned how to control and eradicate abaca diseases. Before the project was introduced, farmers just simply tumbled and removed the infected abaca stalks without killing the prime causes of the disease, the aphids, which were the vector of the abaca viruses. Because of their old practice of disease control and eradication, the aphids were disturbed and spread to other abaca plants.

When ADMP was introduced in the area, farmers became trained in applying better agricultural practices such as the correct use of herbicide and insecticide to kill vectors responsible in transmitting the disease, soaking of bamboo sticks to chemicals then puncturing them into diseased abaca plants. Other infected plants were rouged and burned. Among the said practices, it was believed that the spread of disease could be best controlled by using chemicals.

4.4. Correlation Amongst Socio-Demographic Profiles, Increased in Abaca Fiber Harvested, and Perception on the Success of the Project

Table 4 presents the correlation between the socio-demographic profiles, increased in abaca fiber harvested and perception on the success of the project by the respondents. The status of ownership and size of the farm being cultivated had no correlation with the increased in abaca fiber harvested and the respondents' perception on the success of the project. This means that change in status of the

ownership and the size of the farm did not influence either the increase or decrease of abaca fiber harvested as well as the respondents' perception on the success of the project.

In the meantime, membership in cooperative or association of farmer-beneficiaries had negative correlation to the increase in abaca fiber harvested and no correlation to the respondents' perception on the success of the project. This implied that farmer-beneficiaries who were members of the cooperative were not exempt in experiencing a decrease in harvested fiber. For example, in Barangays Balasbas and Buyo, many farmers who were members of the cooperative still suffered from no increase in abaca production due to typhoon and continuous presence of abaca diseases.

In addition, the respondents' role in abaca fiber production had a high degree of correlation with the increased fiber production; and medium degree of correlation to the farmer-beneficiaries' perception on the success of the project. It means that respondents who were engaged in fiber stripping only had a greater chance of producing high volume of abaca fiber. Also, the abaca farmer's role had a positive correlation with their perception that abaca disease control and eradication conducted by PhilFIDA was successful.

Meanwhile, age, sex, civil status, education and the number of children of the respondents had no correlation with the increased abaca fiber harvested, and with the perception on the success of the project by the respondents.

Lastly, increased in abaca fiber harvested had a positive correlation to the FBs perception on the success of the project. This indicates that farmer-beneficiaries who had experienced an increased in abaca fiber production were likely had positive perception on the outcome of the project.

Table 4.2

Correlation analysis of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, increased in abaca fiber harvested and FBs perception on the success of the project

Socio-demographic Profiles of the Respondents	Increased in Abaca Fiber Harvested	Farmer-Beneficiaries Perception on the Success of the Project
Status of land being cultivated	0.242	0.161
Size of the farm	-0.038	-0.054
Member of the cooperative	-0.287*	-0.026
FBs role in abaca farming	0.543**	0.403**
Age	0.196	-0.005
Sex	0.052	0.094
Civil status	0.150	0.239
Education	0.127	0.066
Number of children	0.055	-0.041
Increased in abaca fiber harvested		0.384**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was conducted in order to assess the success and impact of the Abaca Disease Management Project to abaca farmers. The abaca disease control and eradication was implemented by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in four barangays of Manito, Albay due to high incidence of abaca disease.

The present study was carried out thru gathering of secondary data and survey method by using a prepared questionnaire. Secondary data was utilized to quantitatively analyze the effectiveness of the project. While, primary data were gathered thru the use of a questionnaire to collect information on socio-demographic profiles, socio-economic impact, gender equality impact, impact on social-capital, and other impacts. Moreover, the correlation among socio-demographic profile, impact of the project, and respondents' perception on the success of the project were determined.

Based on secondary data, it was demonstrated that the Abaca Disease Management Project conducted by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority was effective in controlling and eradicating abaca diseases.

There were 57 farmer-beneficiaries interviewed: 16 from Balasbas, 13 from Buyo, 14 from Cawayan, and 14 from Nagotgot. More than half (70%) of respondents were still in productive age ranging from 20-60 years old. Out of the 57 respondents, only two youths are engaged in abaca farming. This implied that abaca farmers were in their aging stage especially those from Barangays Cawayan and Nagotgot. It was also observed that 63.16% of the respondents were male. As to civil status, 89.47%

of the respondents were married. Majority of households in the area were engaged in abaca farming. Most of the families had four and above number of children.

Majority of abaca farmer-respondents were elementary graduate at 50.88% of the total number of respondents. Three respondents were college graduates, which comprised 5.26% of the total respondents.

Aside from abaca farming, farmer-beneficiaries of the project were also engaged in tiger grass cultivation, coconut, rice, and vegetable farming. Some respondents were business owner, laborer, government employee and privately employed.

Large number of respondents interviewed at 89.47% believed that ADMP was successful. Those farmer-respondents claiming that the project was not successful did not experience increase in harvest, while diseases continuously prevailed in their farms.

All respondents from Barangays Cawayan and Nagotgot noticed the increase in abaca fiber harvested that brought them income. In Barangay Buyo, the majority (87.50%) of respondents also observed the increase in abaca fiber harvested. On the contrary, in Barangay Buyo, only 15.38% experienced the increased in income. Most of the farmers did not experience increase in abaca fiber produced due to typhoon that devastated their abaca farms.

As expressed by the respondents, the major contributions of ADMP to the farmer's households were increased in fiber harvested, families being able to send their children to school, and abaca farming becoming their major source of income.

In terms of gender equality impact of the project, women equally had the chance to participate in community organizations. For example, in Barangay Balasbas, women had membership in the abaca farmers' association. Usually, women were not involved

in abaca fiber production since the quality of fiber produced in the area was intended solely for handicraft making. Also, there were plenty of raw materials for women to make handicraft products at home.

Only small portion of the respondents became members of the organization at 19.30%. The farmer-beneficiaries who were given access to transportation through Farm-to-Market Road (FMR) and credit assistance were only 17.54%. Most of the respondents believed that because of the project, solidarity developed among all the respondents from barangays of Cawayan and Nagotgot.

In addition, training and skill development programs expanded which were attended by the farmer-beneficiaries such as training on abaca disease control and eradication method conducted by the implementing agency of the project. Women were also trained in handicraft making and product development out of abaca fiber. Furthermore, the change in management of their abaca farms especially in disease management and also through the trainings given by PhilFIDA helped the farmer-beneficiaries to gain knowledge on how to control and eradicate abaca diseases.

The status of ownership of the land being cultivated, the size of the farm, the age, the sex, the civil status, the education, and the number of children had negligible correlation to the increased in abaca fiber harvested and the respondents' perception on the success of the project. While being a member of the cooperative had negative correlation to the increase in abaca fiber harvested, there was no correlation to the perception on the success of the project. In addition, farmer-beneficiaries' role in abaca farming had high and middle degree of correlation to the increase in abaca fiber harvested and also to the perception on the success of the project. Lastly, increased in abaca fiber harvested by farmers had positive correlation to their perception that ADMP is a successful project.

Therefore, the study concludes that:

1. Abaca farmers must be informed and educated about the importance of formation of cooperative or farmers' association in order for them to easily access the services and programs of the government. Most government projects were dedicated to farmers' cooperative because it is easy to implement and monitor. Having a cooperative made them become aware of government services from technology transfer, skills development and grant;
2. The role of the farmer-beneficiaries on the abaca fiber production had influence on the quantity of fiber harvested;
3. Abaca farmer's role in abaca farming had correlation to the respondent's perception on the success of the project;
4. Increased in fiber harvested by farmer-beneficiaries, gave positive perception on the success of the project; and
5. Abaca Disease Management Project was effective in dealing with disease control and eradication based from analysed secondary data and success perception of the majority of respondents.

It was found that in secondary data gathered that the ADMP implemented by PhilFIDA in four barangays of Manito, Albay such as Barangays Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot was effective in controlling and eradicating abaca diseases.

The effectiveness of ADMP in controlling and eradicating the diseases was in parallel to the result of interview conducted, where 89.47% of respondents agreed that it was a successful project as there was an increased in their fiber harvested due to eradication of diseases.

However, it was reported during interview with Mr. Marlon Rebanco, Head of Technical Assistance Unit (TAU) of PhilFIDA Region V, that the monitoring of disease incidence after the treatment was conducted on 2017. There was no succeeding monitoring conducted on the following years since the objective of the project was already met on the first year of the project implementation as reflected on the results of monitoring and evaluation. The objective of the project was to reduce the disease incidence to less than 5% which consider manageable at farmer's level. In a case of ADMP in Manito, Albay, it was reduced to 2.88%. After five years of project implementation, abaca farmers had continuously observed the presence of disease and there was a need to validate and profile the existence of disease for immediate action. The areas must be monitored again by technical personnel from PhilFIDA if the presence of abaca diseases were still within the manageable level of farmers.

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2009 National Survey of Areas Planted to Abaca

Appendices

Appendix A

Letter to Executive Director Kennedy T. Costales

12 October 2021

KENNEDY T. COSTALES
Executive Director III
This Office

Thru: **Engr. Orlando D. Cocal**
OIC, Technical Assistance Division

Mary Anne R. Molina
OIC, PhilFIDA Regional Office V

Dear **Director Costales**:

This refers to the proposed study by the undersigned as a requirement for the completion of my master's degree at the University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna, taking Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management. As a graduating student, one of the requirements is to undertake and complete a Special Problem that we are required to conduct a study that will contribute to the management of the environment and natural resources.

Furthermore, the study will focus on the effectiveness of the Abaca Disease Management Project conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay. Thus, based on the methodology to be used in the study, the following secondary data are needed as inputs to the study:

1. Land area subjected for disease control and eradication (in ha)
2. Name and no. of farmer-beneficiaries
3. Actual area treated
4. Effective area treated
5. Disease incidence before eradication (in %)
6. Disease incidence after eradication (in %)

The undersigned would also conduct actual field interviews with abaca farmers in the area to assess the impact/contribution of the project.

In line with this, I may request the abovementioned data needed in the study as well as your permission to utilize such information as inputs to the study to be conducted. The said data will be treated confidentially and will be used for academic purposes only.

I am hoping for your favorable response on this matter.

Thank you.

Respectfully yours,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
Fiber Development Officer II

Appendix B
Letter to OIC-Regional Director Mary Anne R. Molina

16 November 2021

MARY ANNE R. MOLINA
OIC, Regional Office V
Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority
Bicol University Compound, Legazpi City, 4500

Dear Ms. Molina:

Greetings!!!

The undersigned is currently pursuing a Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management at the University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. As a graduating student, one of the requirements is to undertake and complete a Special Problem that we are required to conduct a study that will contribute to the management of the environment and natural resources.

In line with this, the undersigned is currently working on the assessment of the Abaca Disease Management Program conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay. I would like to ask permission to access the following documents and data gathered as inputs to the study:

1. Land area subjected for disease control and eradication (in hectare)
2. Name and no. of farmer-beneficiaries
3. Actual area treated
4. Effective area treated
5. Disease incidence before eradication (in %)
6. Disease incidence after eradication (in %)

Also, one of the activities of the study is to conduct a face-to-face interview with abaca farmer-beneficiaries to determine the impact of the project.

As prior to the conduct of the said activity, I humbly request for technical personnel from your good office to accompany me in the area and assist in selecting respondents during the actual interview on November 29 to December 03, 2021.

I am hoping for your favorable response on this matter.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
Fiber Development Officer II

Okay, approved!
Eng. Brent Marbella will assist you during the interview.

for
Mr. Marlon R - ple provide the baseline data.

Scanned with CamScanner

Appendix C

Letter to Mayor Joshua Mari C. Daep

17 November 2021

HON. JOSHUA MARI C. DAEP
Mayor
Municipality of Manito
Province of Albay

Thru: **Mr. Ciriaco P. Padre**
Municipal Agriculturist

Dear **Mayor Daep**,

I am Clark B. Barquilla, an employee of the Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority, an attached agency of the Department of Agriculture, taking Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management at University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. As a graduating student, one of the requirements is to conduct a study on the management of the environment and natural resources.

In line with this, the undersigned is currently working on the assessment of the Abaca Disease Management Project conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay. One of the activities of the study is to conduct a face-to-face interview with abaca farmer-beneficiaries to determine the impact of the project.

As I conduct the data gathering, I humbly request assistance from your good office in identifying abaca farmers in the area, as well as technical personnel to accompany me in selecting fifty (50) abaca farmers as my respondents during the actual interview on November 29 to December 03, 2021.

Please be assured that health and safety protocol on Covid-19 will be observed.

If you have any questions, please contact me at Mobile No. 0939-919-1292.

I am hoping for your favorable response on this matter.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
MENRM Student
UPOU, Los Baños, Laguna

Hand by:

11/17/21
9:10 AM

Appendix D

Letter to Barangay Captain Jessie D. Payte

17 November 2021

HON. JESSIE D. PAYTE
Punong Barangay
Brgy. Balasbas, Manito, Albay

Dear **Hon. Payte**,

Marhay na Aldaw!!!

Ako po si Engr. Clark B. Barquilla, empleyado ng Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority na matatagpuan ang aming ahensiya sa Lungsod ng Quezon, Kalakhang Maynila at kasalukuyang kumukuha ng kursong Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management sa University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. Bilang bahagi ng aking pagtatapos ay kailangan ko po na gumawa ng pananaliksik na may kinalaman sa pangangalaga ng likas na yaman at isa po ang inyong lugar sa napili ko para gawin ang aking pananaliksik o research.

Kaugnay nito, ako ay magsasagawa ng research na may pamagat na "Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Program conducted by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay" na isa ang inyong barangay sa mga benepisaryo ng nasabing proyekto. Layunin ko po na makapanayam ang mga magsasaka sa larangan ng pag-aabaka para sa pagkuha ko ng mga datus na makakatulong sa aking research.

Sa pagsasagawa ng aking panayam, ako po ay may mababang-loob na humihiling na ako po ay inyong tulungan sa pagpapaabot ng impormasyon sa mga benepisaryo ng ADMP para sila ay makadalo sa gaganaping panayam sa ika-29 ng Nobyembre, 2021. Kung maaari po ang panayam ay gagawin ko na lamang sa inyong Barangay Hall o anumang pasilidad na pwedeng pagdausan ng nasabing aktibidad.

Kung kayo po ay may mga katanungan sa nasabing aktibidad maaari ninyo akong tawagan sa oras na komportable sa inyo sa numerong ito 09399191292.

Sana ay mapagbigyan ninyo ako sa aking kahilingan.

Dios Mabalos.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
MENRM Student
UPOU, Los Baños, Laguna

Appendix E

Letter to Barangay Captain Benito A. Gualvez

17 November 2021

HON. BENITO A. GUALVEZ
Punong Barangay
Brgy. Buyo, Manito, Albay

Dear **Hon. Gualvez**,

Marhay na Aldaw!!!

Ako po si Engr. Clark B. Barquilla, empleyado ng Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority na matatagpuan ang aming ahensiya sa Lungsod ng Quezon, Kalakhang Maynila at kasalukuyang kumukuha ng kursong Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management sa University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. Bilang bahagi ng aking pagtatapos ay kailangan ko po na gumawa ng pananaliksik na may kinalaman sa pangangalaga ng likas na yaman at isa po ang inyong lugar sa napili ko para gawin ang aking pananaliksik o research.

Kaugnay nito, ako ay magsasagawa ng research na may pamagat na "Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Program conducted by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay" na isa ang inyong barangay sa mga benepisaryo ng nasabing proyekto. Layunin ko po na makapanayam ang mga magsasaka sa larangan ng pag-aabaka para sa pagkuha ko ng mga datos na makakatulong sa aking research.

Sa pagsasagawa ng aking panayam, ako po ay may mababang-loob na humihiling na ako po ay inyong tulungan sa pagpapaabot ng impormasyon sa mga benepisaryo ng ADMP para sila ay makadalo sa gaganaping panayam sa ika-1 ng Desyembre, 2021. Kung maaari po ang panayam ay gagawin ko na lamang sa inyong Barangay Hall o anumang pasilidad na pwedeng pagdausan ng nasabing aktibidad.

Kung kayo po ay may mga katanungan sa nasabing aktibidad maaari ninyo akong tawagan sa oras na komportable sa inyo sa numerong ito 09399191292.

Sana ay mapagbigyan ninyo ako sa aking kahilingan.

Dios Mabalos.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
MENRM Student
UPOU, Los Baños, Laguna

*Received Copy
Brgy. Chairman - Buyo*

Appendix F

Letter to Barangay Captain Anita B. Ardales

17 November 2021

HON. ANITA B. ARDALES
Punong Barangay
Brgy. Cawayan, Manito, Albay

Dear **Hon. Ardales**,

Marhay na Aldaw!!!

Ako po si Engr. Clark B. Barquilla, empleyado ng Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority na matatagpuan ang aming ahensiya sa Lungsod ng Quezon, Kalakhang Maynila at kasalukuyang kumukuha ng kursong Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management sa University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. Bilang bahagi ng aking pagtatapos ay kailangan ko po na gumawa ng pananaliksik na may kinalaman sa pangangalaga ng likas na yaman at isa po ang inyong lugar sa napili ko para gawin ang aking pananaliksik o research.

Kaugnay nito, ako ay magsasagawa ng research na may pamagat na "Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Program conducted by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay" na isa ang inyong barangay sa mga benepisaryo ng nasabing proyekto. Layunin ko po na makapanayam ang mga magsasaka sa larangan ng pag-aabaka para sa pagkuha ko ng mga datos na makakatulong sa aking research.

Sa pagsasagawa ng aking panayam, ako po ay may mababang-loob na humihiling na ako po ay inyong tulungan sa pagpapaabot ng impormasyon sa mga benepisaryo ng ADMP para sila ay makadalo sa gaganaping panayam sa ika-2 ng Desyembre, 2021. Kung maaari po ang panayam ay gagawin ko na lamang sa inyong Barangay Hall o anumang pasilidad na pwedeng pagdausan ng nasabing aktibidad.

Kung kayo po ay may mga katanungan sa nasabing aktibidad maaari ninyo akong tawagan sa oras na komportable sa inyo sa numerong ito 09399191292.

Sana ay mapagbigyan ninyo ako sa aking kahilingan.

Dios Mabalos.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
MENRM Student
UPOU, Los Baños, Laguna

Appendix G

Letter to Barangay Captain Juan A. Ortiz

17 November 2021

HON. JUAN A. ORTIZ
Punong Barangay
Brgy. Nagotgot, Manito, Albay

Dear **Hon. Ortiz**,

Marhay na Aldaw!!!

Ako po si Engr. Clark B. Barquilla, empleyado ng Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority na matatagpuan ang aming ahensiya sa Lungsod ng Quezon, Kalakhang Maynila at kasalukuyang kumukuha ng kursong Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management sa University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna. Bilang bahagi ng aking pagtatapos ay kailangan ko po na gumawa ng pananaliksik na may kinalaman sa pangangalaga ng likas na yaman at isa po ang inyong lugar sa napili ko para gawin ang aking pananaliksik o research.

Kaugnay nito, ako ay magsasagawa ng research na may pamagat na "Assessment of Abaca Disease Management Program conducted by Philippine Fiber Industry Development Authority in Manito, Albay" na isa ang inyong barangay sa mga benepisaryo ng nasabing proyekto. Layunin ko po na makapanayam ang mga magsasaka sa larangan ng pag-aabaka para sa pagkuha ko ng mga datus na makakatulong sa aking research.

Sa pagsasagawa ng aking panayam, ako po ay may mababang-loob na humihiling na ako po ay inyong tulungan sa pagpapaabot ng impormasyon sa mga benepisaryo ng ADMP para sila ay makadalo sa gaganaping panayam sa ika-3 ng Desyembre, 2021. Kung maaari po ang panayam ay gagawin ko na lamang sa inyong Barangay Hall o anumang pasilidad na pwedeng pagdausan ng nasabing aktibidad.

Kung kayo po ay may mga katanungan sa nasabing aktibidad maaari ninyo akong tawagan sa oras na komportable sa inyo sa numerong ito 09399191292.

Sana ay mapagbigyan ninyo ako sa aking kahilingan.

Dios Mabalos.

Sincerely,

CLARK B. BARQUILLA
MENRM Student
UPOU, Los Baños, Laguna

Appendix H

Documentations

Assessment of ADMP of PhilFIDA in Manito, Albay

Appendix H – Questionnaire

ASSESSMENT OF ABACA DISEASE MANAGEMENT PROGRAM OF PHILIPPINE FIBER INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY IN MANITO, ALBAY

The ADMP project conducted by PhilFIDA in Manito Albay which covers four (4) barangays namely: Balasbas, Buyo, Cawayan and Nagotgot was started in 2016. This questionnaire wishes to determine the impacts on the household beneficiaries of the project. It will also serve in the formulation of recommendations based on the data that will be gathered. Please answer honestly. Thank you.

A. SITE IDENTIFICATION

- | | | | |
|--------------|-------|------------------|-------|
| 1. Region: | _____ | 3. Municipality: | _____ |
| 2. Province: | _____ | 4. Barangay: | _____ |

B. RESPONDENT IDENTIFICATION

1. Name of Respondent: _____
2. Address (Purok/Sitio/Zone): _____
3. Contact Information: _____
4. Status of land being cultivated:

1 – Owned	4 – Rented
2 – Tenant	5 – Inherited
3 – Awarded Through Agrarian Reform	6 – Others

5. Size of the farm being cultivated (in hectare)

1 – Less than one

2 – One

3 - Two

4 – Three and above

6. Are you a member of a cooperative/association?

1 – Yes

2 – No

7. If yes, what is the name of the cooperative/association? _____

8. Respondent role in abaca farming:

1 – *Tuxero*

2 – Stripper

3 – *Tuxero*/Stripper

4 – Trader

5 – Processor

6 – Others, specify: _____

C. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

<p>1. Age</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) 20 – 302.) 31 – 403.) 41 – 504.) 51 – 605.) 61 and above <p>2. Sex</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) Male2.) Female <p>3. Civil Status</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) Single2.) Married	<p>4. Highest Educational Attainment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) Did not finish Elementary2.) Elementary Graduate3.) Did not finish High School4.) High School Graduate5.) Vocational Course6.) College Undergraduate7.) College Graduate <p>5. Source of income aside from Abaca Farming</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) Government employment2.) Private employment3.) Business owner	<p>6. No. of children</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.) One2.) Two3.) Three4.) Four and above <p>If above, specify: _____</p>
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3.) Legally separated 4.) Annulled 5.) Widowed	4.) Rice farming 5.) Coconut farming 6.) Tiger grass (<i>talahib</i>) farming 7.) Vegetable farming 8.) Fishing 9.) Laborer 10.) Other	
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D. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE PROJECT

<p>1. Is there an increase of fiber harvested after the project was implemented in 2016?</p> <p>1.) Yes If Yes, how much the percent increase annually from 2017 ____, 2018 ____, 2019 ____, 2020 ____, 2021 ____?</p> <p>2.) No If No, why not? _____</p> <p>2. Is there an increase in income after the project was implemented?</p> <p>1.) Yes If Yes, what is the monthly average increase? _____</p> <p>2.) No If No, why was there no increase? _____</p> <p>3. Where was the increased income used for?</p> <p>1.) Education 5.) House Repair/Construction</p>	<p>4. Do you feel that ADMP was a successful project?</p> <p>1.) Yes, If Yes, Why? _____</p> <p>2.) No, If No, Why? _____</p> <p>5. In your opinion, what is the major contribution of the project in your household?</p> <p>1.) Become major source of livelihood 2.) Increase in income 3.) Enable parents to send children to school 4.) Others, specify: _____ 5.) None</p>
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2.) Food	6.) Home Furniture	
3.) Clothing	7.) Services/Utilities	
4.) Medicine	8.) Others, Specify _____	

E. GENDER EQUALITY IMPACTS	
1. Did the project have an effect on the following? 1.) Women’s participation in community organizations (Please explain) 2.) Women’s involvement in production activities (Please explain) 3.) Women’s role in the family (Please explain) 4.) Women’s income (Please explain) 5.) Husband and wife roles in the household? (Please explain)	
F. IMPACT ON SOCIAL CAPITAL	G. OTHER IMPACTS
1. Please answer with “Yes” or “No” the following questions: 1.) Did the project cause farmers to become members of associations? Please elaborate. 2.) Did the project help farmers to get access to various community services (transportation, credit, water, sanitation, health, etc.? Please explain. 3.) Did the project cause solidarity among members of the community? Please explain.	1. Did the project have a contribution to the following? 1.) Increase in training and skills development attended 2.) Abaca farming as stable source of income (Please explain) 3.) Abaca farming comparing to other crops as source of livelihood (Please explain) 4.) Change in management in abaca farming before and after the project was implemented (Please explain)

Thank you for your participation.